

The effects of live vs. pre-recorded monochord sounds on healthy adults: Study protocol for a crossover randomized controlled trial

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Chronic stress significantly impacts physical and mental health, encouraging the exploration of stress regulation methods, including music therapy. Live monochord sounds, known for their calming properties, are a promising tool, yet studies comparing live and pre-recorded music are limited. This study aims to examine the effects of live vs. pre-recorded monochord sounds on the autonomic nervous system response, such as heart rate variability (HRV) and electrodermal activity (EDA), and explore possible associations between physiological data, social connectedness, and musical attributes in a dyadic setting.

Method: In a crossover randomized controlled trial, healthy adults aged 20–29 ($n = 66$) will be assigned to a session with either live or pre-recorded monochord sounds. After a washout period they will receive one or the other intervention. Pre-, peri-, and post-intervention measurements will be taken using consistent instruments for both conditions. Physiological parameters (heart rate variability, respiration rate, skin resistance) and psychological parameters (validated questionnaires, subjective experience surveys) will be collected from the participants and music therapists, and musical parameters (audio and video recordings of monochord playing) will be captured.

Discussion: Findings may inform therapy and patient self-use, advancing understanding of music's role in stress regulation. Investigating why and how monochord sounds affect stress could enhance training and interventions in music therapy. This initial focus on healthy adults could be followed by a clinical phase involving individuals with stress-related diseases.

ARTICLE HISTORY Received 22 January 2025; Accepted 1 June 2025

KEYWORDS Receptive music therapy; monochord; stress regulation; healthy adults; heart rate variability; synchronization

Introduction

In music therapy, receptive interventions are often applied with the specific aim of strengthening stress-regulation capabilities, creating opportunities for relaxation and

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 Supplemental data for this article can be accessed online at <https://doi.org/10.1080/08098131.2025.2524859>

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introspection. Frequently, these interventions feature sedative music, characterized by its soothing, flowing nature, minimal variations in pitch, dynamics, or rhythm (Radocy & Boyle, 1979). Within receptive music therapy, there are various applications of pre-recorded music, such as during surgical procedures (Bringman et al., 2009) or in the context of Guided Imagery and Music (GIM) (McKinney & Honig, 2016). Most forms of receptive music therapy use pre-recorded music (Grocke, 2016).

In this crossover randomized controlled trial, a receptive intervention of music therapy using live vs. pre-recorded monochord sounds is investigated to examine its effects on the autonomic nervous system response, which plays a major role in stress regulation through the balance between the parasympathetic (rest and digest) and sympathetic (fight or flight) systems (Gibbons, 2019). Stress regulation in this protocol is defined by the autonomic system's activity, with heart rate variability (HRV) indicating parasympathetic regulation and electrodermal activity (EDA) reflecting sympathetic activation. In a wider scope, these effects can be framed within a physiological perspective on stress regulation. The study also aims to explore the intersubjective dynamics of the intervention within a dyadic setting, examining the physiological and psychological interplay between the therapist and the participant through simultaneous measurements.

Background

The monochord in music therapy

The monochord is an instrument with a hollow wooden resonating body. A total of 33 long strings are attached, all of which are tuned to the same tone. By evenly stroking the strings with a consistent tempo and pressure, the main pitch is audible along with the corresponding overtones, producing a rich, continuous soundscape (Dosch & Timmermann, 2005; Trost, 2021). According to various studies, live monochord sounds are particularly suitable in receptive music therapy (Bossert & Marz, 2012; De Witte et al., 2019; Gäbel et al., 2017, 2019; Schäfer, 2014). In German-speaking countries, live receptive interventions, where the therapist plays music for the patient, are called “Für-Spiel”, which means playing for someone (Timmermann, 2004, p. 18). The intervention involves the therapist's intentional playing that is tailored to the individual's needs and used to address emotions, promote relaxation or prepare the patient for deeper therapeutic work (Frohne-Hagemann, 2004, 2020; Timmermann, 2004). Receptive music therapy involving the monochord is primarily utilized clinically when a relaxing or calming effect is desired. This intervention can be adapted to other approaches using instruments like the body tambura or a monochord sound bed. Unlike vibroacoustic therapy, the monochord is played live rather than using mechanical vibrations.

Upon closer examination of the studies on the effects of monochord music, it becomes apparent that in nearly all cases, monochord music is not used in isolation, but in combination with speaking, singing, or breathing activities (Fuchs et al., 2015; Gäbel et al., 2017; Rose & Weis, 2008; Teckenberg-Jansson et al., 2019; Warth et al., 2015). Additionally, the control interventions vary. Some studies feature no control interventions (Ranger et al., 2018; Warth et al., 2015), while others use relaxation music from various genres alone or in combination with speaking, singing, and breathing (Fuchs et al., 2015; Sandler et al., 2016). In one study, participants in the control group

listened to verbal relaxation instructions (Gäbel et al., 2017). In another investigation, the individual lies quietly in a bed (Teckenberg-Jansson et al., 2019) or remains still on a sound bed (Bieligmeyer et al., 2018). Some studies examine physiological parameters such as HRV (Gäbel et al., 2017; Lee & Bhattacharya, 2013; Teckenberg-Jansson et al., 2019; Warth et al., 2015), electroencephalogram (EEG) or EDA (Fachner et al., 2021; Sandler et al., 2016), and others evaluate the results qualitatively without incorporating physiological parameters (Bieligmeyer et al., 2018; Schröter, 2007). The instruments differ across the individual studies as well. Some use the monochord (Fuchs et al., 2015; Gäbel et al., 2017) and others apply vibro-acoustic instruments such as sound lounges or sound chairs (Bieligmeyer et al., 2018; Delmastro et al., 2018; Dill-Schmölders & Grün, 2012; Sandler et al., 2016; Warth et al., 2015), or pentatonic harp-like instruments (children's harp, Tao lyre) (Bieligmeyer et al., 2018; Ranger et al., 2018; Teckenberg-Jansson et al., 2019). In addition to the pentatonic tuning, two other tunings based on fifths are described (Tao tuning, fifths tuning). In the Tao tuning, the tones used are h, a, e, and d with the pitch of a'432 Hz (Bieligmeyer et al., 2018). In the fifths tuning, the tones used are a, c, and d (Rose & Weis, 2008; Sandler et al., 2008). In some studies, no information is provided regarding the tuning of the instrument (Fuchs et al., 2015; Gäbel et al., 2017; Lee & Bhattacharya, 2013; Schröter, 2007) and one study employs electronically generated sine tones without specifying pitch (Delmastro et al., 2018). To date, findings are not directly comparable due to diverging designs, music therapy methods, and control interventions.

State of the art of live vs. pre-recorded receptive music therapy

The effectiveness of receptive music therapy is well documented in various areas; however, few studies have examined the difference between music therapy using live-played music and music played from audio recordings. In a qualitative design, Garabedian and Kelly (2020) investigated the effects of live-played cello music and pre-recorded music on individuals with dementia and their caregivers, but did not directly compare the differing effects of the two delivery methods. In a randomized controlled study, Bush et al. (2021) demonstrated that live music played for patients in a pediatric intensive care unit resulted in a significant reduction in heart rate compared to playing pre-recorded music. In a randomized case-control study comparing live music to pre-recorded music during an MRI examination, it was demonstrated that individuals who received live music experienced shorter scan times and fewer interruptions during the examinations (Walworth, 2010). Further, Silverman (2003, 2016) found no difference in the effects of live music versus pre-recorded music among both psychotic patients and those with addiction disorders undergoing withdrawal. Another study found that while both active music therapy and music listening significantly improved symptoms in patients with schizophrenia, the music listening group showed greater improvements in negative symptoms, depression, and functioning, whereas the active music therapy group showed better therapeutic alliance and quality of life (Hannibal et al., 2023). Harding et al. (2023) published a study protocol in which she aimed to investigate the comparison between live vs. pre-recorded music on the extent of postoperative pain. Gelatti et al. (2020) revealed that live harp playing reduces pre-operative stress more than harp playing from recorded sources. Parameters evaluated included heart rate (HR) and blood pressure (BP). Since this was a non-randomized

case-control study, she recommended conducting further investigations under randomized conditions.

A physiological perspective on stress regulation

Globally, the prevalence of stress is a major concern (American Psychological Association [APA], 2020; World Health Organization [WHO], 2024). A systematic review showed that exposure to frequent stressors and repeated psychological arousal can create a state of chronic stress. Symptoms include an overall lack of adaptation to repeated stressors and inability to switch off the stress response after a stressor has passed, resulting in an allostatic response that is insufficient to cope with the stressor, leading to poorer health outcomes (Guidi et al., 2021). Stress can also be regarded as a physiological response to environmental stressors and challenges. These include autonomic and hormonal reactions to stressors that can induce perspiration, accelerated respiration and muscular tension, which can also be interpreted as preparatory action for potential responses (Fink, 2016).

Biomarkers of stress regulation

In clinical settings, a common biomarker to assess stress regulation is heart rate variability (HRV). HRV refers to the extent of variation in the time between two heartbeats. This time between two heartbeats is called the “R-R interval” – it is measured from one R-wave to the next R-wave on an electrocardiogram (ECG), which are the sharp peaks in the heart signal. To calculate HRV, the R-R intervals are recorded over a certain period. Then, the variation – or difference – between these intervals is analyzed using statistical or mathematical methods. A high HRV typically indicates that the body’s autonomic nervous system can adapt well to stress or changes. A low HRV may indicate stress, fatigue, or reduced recovery ability.

A recent analysis of current literature showed that HRV is a practical biomarker for resilience and mental health and HRV depicts a global index of an individual’s flexibility and adaptability to stressors (Perna et al., 2020). Beauchaine and Thayer (2015) consider HRV to be a relevant biomarker for evaluating self-regulation or other dimensions of psychopathology. HRV is not only linked to the capacity to regulate physiological arousal but also to various psychological and behavioral variables typically addressed in psychotherapeutic interventions (Petrocchi & Cheli, 2019). Specific training for stress regulation has already been used for many decades in the form of HRV biofeedback in professional sport settings, as well as in the treatment of diverse physical and emotional disorders (Rief & Birbaumer, 2010). Furthermore, the therapeutic use of music has been studied in regard to its effects on stress regulation or the enhancement of HRV (Mojtabavi et al., 2020). In a review by Idrobo-Ávila et al. (2018), common biomarkers in studies during music listening were collected. Electrocardiogram (ECG), HRV, and HR were found to be the most studied, followed by BP, respiration (resp), and EDA. Relaxation-promoting music has been shown to improve HRV (Gäbel et al., 2017, 2019; Koelsch & Jäncke, 2015; Ranger et al., 2018; Teckenberg-Jansson et al., 2019; Warth et al., 2015).

Additionally, regional changes in cardiac activity caused by music-induced emotions have also been demonstrated, though high-quality studies in this area are needed to shed more light on the relationship between HRV and music (Gäbel et al., 2019; Koelsch & Jäncke, 2015; Warth et al., 2015).

Non-invasive therapy approaches to address stress regulation

In addition to suggested lifestyle changes, various approaches are used to improve stress regulation. These include regenerative therapies, relaxation techniques, physical activities, biofeedback, medication, and psychotherapy. Both physiological and psychological methods are used for non-specific stress-related complaints (WHO, 2022). Specific psychotherapeutic methods include: problem-solving training, cognitive training, enjoyment training, social support, goal clarification, time management strategies, and skills training (Kaluza, 2023). As the prevalence of stress is increasing, non-invasive therapies such as music therapy for stress-related disorders are especially indicated (Maniero et al., 2023).

Music therapy and stress regulation

Music therapy is a non-invasive, multisensory treatment approach often grounded in a bio-psycho-social framework, emphasizing the interaction between biological, psychological, and social factors, as music influences both the body and the mind (Bruscia, 2014; Dileo, 2021). In treatment settings, music therapy and other creative arts therapies such as dance/movement, visual arts and drama are increasingly employed. They are considered innovative ways to prevent stress and to improve stress management through music-assisted relaxation (Wheeler, 2015). Music therapy's effects on stress regulation include decreased physiological arousal, tension reduction, and decreased intensity of stress-related emotional states (De Witte et al., 2019, 2020). Stegemann (2020) conceptually summarized neurobiological connections, specifically regarding the relaxation-promoting effect of music, in the music-related neurobiological relaxation model (MNEMO). Bruscia identified multiple clinical goals in receptive music therapy including promoting receptivity, evoking specific somatic responses, stimulating or relaxing the client, developing auditory or motor skills, evoking affective states and experiences, exploring ideas and thoughts, facilitating memory, reminiscence and regression, evoking imagery and fantasies, connecting the listener to a community or sociocultural group, and stimulating peak/spiritual experiences (Bruscia, 1998). In the context of receptive music therapy, pre-recorded music pieces and live music played by the therapist are used (Grocke & Wigram, 2007). In live receptive music therapy interventions, more research is needed on the mechanisms at play to document, understand, and advance the efficacy of these approaches.

Interpersonal synchrony in the context of music therapy

Synchronization is a common experience of everyday life that happens when people naturally coordinate their actions or movements with others. Simple examples include matching facial expressions, walking in unison or crossing legs simultaneously during a conversation. There is increasing interest in studying the synchronization of body movements between patient and therapist as a potential marker for researching the

therapeutic alliance (Koole & Tschacher, 2016; Tschacher & Meier, 2019). Several studies measuring HRV before and during psychotherapeutic sessions revealed HRV patterns correlate with patients' perception of the therapeutic alliance, indicating that the quality of the alliance is rated higher with increased synchrony (Blanck et al., 2019; Ramseyer & Tschacher, 2008; Stratford et al., 2014; Tschacher & Meier, 2019). These results are in line with other data in which people have experiences of interindividual connectedness and synchronization in HRV (McCarty, 2017). Studying synchronization is a way to measure meaningful moments in therapy.

There is broad acceptance that the therapeutic alliance is an important common factor regarding positive therapeutic outcomes, in fact some studies have found that it accounts for as much as 30% of the therapeutic outcome (Martin et al., 2000; Pfammatter & Tschacher, 2016; Tschuschke, 2016; Wampold & Imel, 2015; Wiggins et al., 2012). In music therapy, the relevance of the therapeutic relationship can be regarded as equally relevant as in psychotherapy (Silverman, 2019). A few studies have considered nonverbal and/or physiological parameters when evaluating interpersonal synchronization in the context of active music therapy interventions (Haslbeck, 2014; Neugebauer & Aldridge, 1998; Nielsen & Holck, 2020; Venuti et al., 2016; Yap et al., 2022). Two studies used physiological measures (EEG) to evaluate synchronization in the context of receptive music therapy approaches (Fachner et al., 2021, 2019). In summary, there appears to be a research gap when considering synchronous physiological events and meaningful moments in receptive music therapy settings.

Aims and objectives

In this study, our main aim is to investigate whether the effect of live-played monochord sounds on the autonomic nervous system response of healthy adults differs from the effect of experiencing pre-recorded monochord sounds. The main objective is to understand how these variants affect the autonomic nervous system response to evaluate the therapeutic effects on stress regulation as measured by its corresponding psychophysiological biomarkers (HRV, EDA, Respiration) and through qualitative questionnaires. Results may inform therapeutic techniques and patient self-use of monochord sounds. Additionally, the study pursues the exploratory objective of examining the intersubjective nature of the intervention in a dyadic setting, considering the physiological and psychological interplay between therapist and participant with simultaneous measurements.

Method

Study design

We apply an AB/BA crossover randomized controlled trial to investigate the effects of monochord sounds on healthy adults who will be randomized to Arm A/Live or Arm B/Pre-recorded first, followed by the second version. The protocol has been designed in accordance with the Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials (SPIRIT, 2023) and adheres to its guidelines for interventional trials (Table 1).

Table 1. SPIRIT template for the schedule of enrolment, interventions, and assessments

	PRE-STUDY			STUDY PERIOD		
	Enrolment		Allocation	Post-allocation		
	<i>E-Mail</i>	<i>Online Assessment</i>		<i>Intervention A: Live</i>	<i>Wash Out Period</i>	<i>Control B: Pre-recorded</i>
	$-t_2$	$-t_1$	0	t_1	t_2	t_3
TIMEPOINT DURATION	20 Min.	30 Min.	15 Min.	45 Min.	4 weeks	45 Min.
ENROLMENT:						
Pre-screening	X	X				
Informed consent	X					
Medical assessment		X				
Eligibility screen	X	X				
Randomization			X			
INTERVENTIONS:						
<i>Intervention A: Live</i>				X		X
<i>Control intv. B: Pre-recorded</i>				X		X
ASSESSMENTS:						
Trier Inventory of Chronic Stress (TICS)			X			
Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)			X			
Relaxation State Questionnaire (RSQ)				X		X
Video & audio recording				X		X
Heart rate variability				X		X
Electrodermal activity				X		X
Respiration				X		X
Post-session survey				X		X

Ethical considerations

The study protocol was approved by the Swiss Ethics Committee of Zurich. It was registered with the Swiss National Clinical Trials Portal (SNCTP000005596) on 10 August 2023. The study will comply with the Declaration of Helsinki, ICH-GCP, HRA, and local regulations. Independent monitoring of quality and data procedures will be conducted by University Services. Annual safety reports will be submitted to the Ethics Committee. A trained music therapist will supervise all interventions, ensuring safety and compliance with good clinical practices. Serious adverse events will be documented and reported to the sponsor within 24 hours.

Participants and recruitment

Participants aged 20–29 will be recruited from German-speaking regions of Switzerland through flyers, social media, and email lists reaching institutions such as universities and hospitals. Inclusion criteria include being unmedicated, free of substance abuse or cardiac disease, German-proficient, and providing informed consent. Exclusion criteria are heart disease, arterial hypertension, recent mental illness, medication use, substance abuse, hearing loss, pregnancy, regular heavy smoking (>5 cigarettes/day), music therapy professionals or students. The chosen age group is prioritized based on physiological reasons, as HRV is known to be influenced by age,

gender and medical conditions. Since HRV decreases with advancing age, this specific age group is selected (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1997; Lohninger, 2021; Rief & Birbaumer, 2010; Umetani et al., 1998). To enhance recruitment feasibility, this age group was also selected due to easy access through our academic network. The limitations of this choice will need to be addressed in future publications.

Interventions

Both study arms are administered by trained and experienced music therapists - one with advanced psychotherapy training, supervision and education expertise, the other with international music therapy training, clinical and educational experience - ensuring standardized, proficient delivery of the intervention. A treatment fidelity protocol was tested and piloted, incorporating various playing styles. The monochord sounds were analyzed using power spectrums to visualize the associated overtones, allowing for the determination of pitch and playing speed. The reporting of the music criteria can be found in the online supplemental material using the checklist provided by Robb et al. (2011). Participants remain seated for both treatment sessions, which are conducted by the same therapist to ensure standardization, consistency and to avoid confounding the results. The music therapist and the monochord are present in both live and pre-recorded conditions, with a member of the research team handling the physiological measurements and technical setup.

Arm A intervention – Live setting

In the live setting, music is played without the aid of a visual metronome. The music therapists undergo prior training to adhere to clinically established standards, producing a sound characterized by a flat sound carpet and richness in overtones. The monochord is tuned to the note “g”, which equals 198 Hz.

Arm B control condition – Pre-recorded setting

In contrast, the control condition involves monochord sounds pre-recorded by a music therapist in a studio setting, guided by a visual metronome adhering to established standards. The bowing speed is maintained at approximately 2.5 seconds per hand/33 strings, resulting in a playing frequency of approximately 14 Hertz. This rhythm generates a pattern taking approximately 10 seconds to complete four hand strokes. The audio recording remains consistent across all participants and is played via loudspeakers, with the volume set to a standardized level that approximately matches the volume of the live played sounds.

Study procedures

The study duration for each participant is approximately 5 weeks, consisting of an assessment interview and two 45-minute monochord sound sessions (see [Figure 1](#) and [Table 1](#)). To minimize carryover effects and to control for the influence of varying levels of hormones throughout the menstrual cycle on HRV, a 4-week washout period is allotted between treatment sessions (Schmalenberger et al., 2021). Eligible participants identified via prescreening will receive comprehensive study details and consent form via email, explaining objectives, procedures, risks and benefits. The participants are informed that they will hear two different versions of monochord sounds without

Figure 1. Adapted CONSORT study design flow diagram

revealing what they consist of. After signing and returning the consent form, they undergo an initial screening session with the study doctor, who will gather demographics, medical history, musical preferences and experiences with sports activities and relaxation methods. The assessment of musical preference is an important aspect, as it may be a potential indication for adverse effects to the monochord sounds. In receptive music therapy research, participants’ music preferences have been shown to be conducive to relaxation effects compared to researcher-selected music. However, there is also consensus across studies suggesting specific characteristics to consider when choosing relaxing music when choice is not an option, or the preferred music might be too stimulating (McFerran & Grocke, 2022). Monochord sounds fall within the characteristics of this category. After completing this initial medical interview, the participants will be enrolled in the study and randomized to one of the two

intervention sequences. As HRV exhibits circadian organization, close attention is paid to scheduling both sessions for each participant at the same time of day (Jarczok et al., 2019). Immediately after each monochord session, the participants will be invited to respond to a survey answering questions about their subjective experience. The sessions will take place at a private music therapy practice near the Zurich University of the Arts in Switzerland. Figure 1 shows a schematic overview of the study.

Randomization and masking

A stratified randomization with blocks based on gender (Male, Female, Non-Binary) and age (20–24, 25–29 years) ensures balance between treatment groups to control for HRV differences. Randomization tables are created in the R software and uploaded to REDCap, concealing treatment sequences to avoid selection bias. The next available treatment (AB or BA) is assigned and saved in a Read-Only field. The study is not masked, as therapists must know the intervention modality, which is also visible to participants.

Sample size calculation

The sample size is based on a prior randomized controlled study, “Relaxation Effects of Musically Guided Resonance Breathing” (Fuchs et al., 2018), which compared live monochord music with guided breathing to pre-recorded relaxation music with spontaneous breathing on HRV. This parallel study ($n = 60$) found an effect size of Cohen’s $d = 0.58$. To find an equivalent effect size for a crossover experiment, Cohen’s $d = 0.56$ was calculated using an intraclass correlation (ICC) of 0.5 (Uhlir et al., 2020). For the current study, we expect a smaller effect size due to two differences: participants will breathe spontaneously in both conditions, and the same type of monochord sounds will be played in both conditions, making them more similar. Thus, we estimate an effect size of Cohen’s $d_z = 0.4$, which is in the range between small and medium effect sizes (Quintana, 2016). To achieve 80% power with $\alpha = 0.05$, a minimum sample size of 52 is calculated using G*Power version 3.1. To account for participant dropout and technical issues, adding a 20% buffer brings the final sample size to 66.

Description of study instruments

Biosignal measurement

Various biosignals will be recorded concurrently in both participants and therapists. The following biosignals are captured from the test participants: ECG, respiration, and EDA. ECG readings are obtained using three chest wall electrodes, respiration is monitored through a breathing belt equipped with a stretch sensor, and EDA is measured with two electrodes attached on the palmar surface of the non-dominant hand. These sensors are connected to the NeXus-10 MKII biofeedback device, developed for clinical applications which is compliant with the standards outlined in the Medical Technology Regulation. The sampling rate for all biosignals will be 1024 Hz, as recommended by Peltola (2012). HRV analysis is conducted using the raw ECG data.

Disposable electrodes are utilized to minimize the risk of infection. ECG and respiration data are recorded simultaneously for the therapist.

Measurement of audio signals

Monochord sounds are recorded during each session for sound analysis using Neumann KM184 microphones, positioned above the monochord on both the left and right sides to avoid interfering with interaction. Audio and biosignals are precisely synchronized via a trigger interface in the NeXus system. Each session is video recorded with two cameras to analyze playing movements and monitor interactions between therapist and participant.

Measurement with questionnaires

Before the monochord sessions, acute stress levels and chronic stress levels are assessed using two questionnaires. The Trier Inventory of Chronic Stress (TICS) is used to determine the level of chronic stress, considering six biopsychosocial aspects of chronic stress (Schulz & Schlotz, 1999). The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) consists of 10 items and is used to address the perceived level of stress in the previous month in people aged 12 and above (Klein et al., 2016). Before and after each intervention, short-term relaxation is assessed by the Relaxation State Questionnaire (RSQ) (Steghaus & Poth, 2022). To explore participants' subjective experiences, a survey is administered after each sound intervention (Arm A, Arm B). The music therapist first asks participants to describe any associations, words, or images that come to mind helping shift their consciousness. Participants then complete a written survey with open-ended questions, Likert scales, continuous rating, and categorical responses on bodily sensations, emotions, thoughts, music experience (volume, duration, time perception, therapist connection), and significant moments. The therapist fills out a similar survey. After completion of both sessions, the therapist asks verbal questions to compare experiences and allow space for additional feedback. The survey is available in the online supplemental data.

Outcome measures

Primary outcome

The primary outcome measure for this study focuses on the objective recording of tension levels by assessing relevant parameters of the autonomic nervous system response, such as HRV and EDA. Specifically, the change in the mean value of the Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD) between the baseline before each intervention and the final 5 minutes of the intervention serves as a critical indicator. To analyze HRV, time-domain (TD) methods examine the variance of intervals between normal heartbeats (also called NN) that originate from sinoatrial node depolarizations. The sinoatrial node is the pacemaker of the heart. Electrical activity originating in this section of the heart stimulates the contraction of the heart muscle and causes a heartbeat. RMSSD specifically indicates the parasympathetic component of HRV. Breathing is concurrently assessed to evaluate its effect on HRV, but it is not evaluated as a separate primary endpoint (Lohninger, 2021).

Table 2. Sequence of a 45-minute monochord session

Minutes	5	10	15	20	35
	<i>Pre Music Sequence</i>	<i>Technical setup</i>	<i>Baseline Vanilla Task: Reading</i>	<i>Monochord Sounds Arm A & Arm B</i>	<i>Post Music Sequence</i>
Measurements participant	RSQ – Pre	Attach recording devices	Measure HRV, Resp., EDA Audio & video recording	Measure HRV, Resp., EDA Audio & video recording	RSQ-Post Survey
Measurements music therapist		Attach recording devices	Measure HRV, Resp., Audio & video recording	Measure HRV, Resp., Audio & video recording	Survey

Vital Parameters: Heart rate variability: HRV; Resp.: Respiration; EDA: Electrodermal activity; RSQ: Relaxation State Questionnaire.

Secondary outcomes

Secondary endpoints assess tonic EDA before and during the intervention, as well as the difference in the subjective assessment of relaxation before and after the intervention. The change in EDA will be calculated by measuring the relative changes in skin conductance level (SCL) at two time points (Start versus End of Monochord Sounds). The baseline time point is defined as the moment the music begins, and the post-measurement is taken when the music ends. As EDA varies greatly between individuals, absolute values cannot be considered; only the direction of change itself can be assessed, indicating relaxation or increasing arousal (Boucsein et al., 2012). The subjective estimation of relaxation before and after the intervention will be assessed using the RSQ (Steghaus & Poth, 2022). The chronological design of outcome measurements can be found in Table 2.

Other outcomes and exploratory measures

In the exploratory measurements, we aim to investigate the intersubjective nature of the intervention, with a specific focus on the phenomenon of physiological synchronicity. We intend to examine methods that allow for the representation of synchronicity between audio and biosignals at an individual and interpersonal level. Additionally, we seek to investigate the extent to which inter-individual synchronicity between the test participant and music therapist (player) can be traced on a physiological level (Tschacher & Meier, 2019; Yap et al., 2022). These quantitative results will be compared with participants' qualitative responses regarding their subjective perceived connection to the music therapist and the difference thereof between the two modalities. To evaluate the subjective perceived connection between therapist and participant (as measured by a Continuous Rating Scale), the associations between scores will be compared by treatment using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and Spearman's rho. The potential synchrony between the physiological recordings (heart rate and breath rate) of therapist and participant will be evaluated using the windowed cross-correlation time series analysis method Surrogate Synchrony or SUSY (Tschacher & Meier, 2019). The SUSY model generates surrogate data (randomized versions

of the original physiological signals) by time-shifting one signal to test if the observed synchrony exceeds expected chance. Synchronization of therapist-participant biosignals and audio signals will be analyzed using adapted SUSY, cross-correlation, or time-synchronized signal processing. The sound analysis primarily focuses on subtle and permanent changes within the overtone spectrum (OS). We will analyze the OS from each live intervention and the pre-recorded version for patterns that occur in similar frequency ranges as the physiological data, enabling meaningful comparisons. For example, extracting an OS pattern of approximately 900 milliseconds, which is equivalent to the time duration of an RR interval. We will evaluate whether the synchronicity differs when the monochord sounds are presented live or from a recording.

Data management and confidentiality

The electronic Case Report Form (eCRF) database is securely stored on Zurich University of the Arts' internal servers using REDCap software. All database interactions, including access and modifications, are logged in an immutable format. Data is accessible only to authorized individuals (sponsor, researchers, ethics committee) for study-related tasks. REDCap roles restrict visibility and downloading of identifiers. Participants are assigned a unique alphanumeric code, with no association to their initials, which serves as their exclusive identifier. Identifying information, such as name and email, is not stored in the research database. The participant's birthdate is recorded as "01.01.YYYY" to protect privacy and maintain ethical standards. Source data integrity is maintained by quality control checks and logging of all data entry. Video and audio recordings of all sessions are securely stored and deleted after the study to protect participant privacy. The informed consent process is documented, and the consent form is retained. In case of early withdrawal or consent retraction, the use of data collected will follow study guidelines.

Statistical data analysis

Raw electrocardiogram data will be visually inspected and processed using algorithms to ensure only sinoatrial node depolarizations are counted as heartbeats. Ectopic heartbeats, which are triggered by reflexes in other areas of the heart, will be corrected through interpolation. Interpolation estimates when the heartbeat would have occurred if originating from a sinoatrial node depolarization, thus "normalizing" the irregular heartbeat. Descriptive statistics will be generated using the R software "tableone" package and graphically displayed. Model assumptions will be checked with Q-Q plots of residual errors, Tukey-Anscombe plots, and scatterplots. If necessary, data transformations will be applied. Missing data values will be assumed to be missing at random. The variance between demographics of treatment groups prior to treatment will be evaluated and treatment sequence will be analyzed for potential carryover effects using the "anova" function.

The experimental design includes repeated measures and hierarchical data, with participants grouped by therapist. Linear mixed-effects models will be used, which account for the correlation of repeated measures within individuals and control for therapist-specific effects. Additional models will explore how other variables, added as

fixed or random effects, explain outcome variation. Fixed effects include variables consistently experienced by all participants, such as treatment. Random effects account for variability not directly under investigation, such as environmental factors.

The primary outcome, mean change in RMSSD, will assess the difference between live and pre-recorded monochord sounds on HRV. The mean change in RMSSD is calculated by subtracting the baseline RMSSD from the RMSSD score during the last 5 minutes of treatment. Variables such as participant, baseline RMSSD, breath rate, therapist, tempo, and room temperature may be added as random or fixed effects. Interactions between variables will be evaluated to see if one variable's effect depends on another. Participant EDA will be evaluated based on the percent change in skin conductance from the beginning to the end of each treatment period. Additional analyses may include room humidity, room temperature, BMI, and sex as fixed or random effects.

P-values will be calculated using Satterthwaite's approximation. A two-sided alpha level of 0.05 is assumed for all significant tests, as our hypothesis tests for any difference between treatments. Sensitivity analyses will evaluate baseline imbalances and robustness of results by comparing primary outcomes with/without outliers, complete vs. all cases, effects of clustering by therapist, and treatment sequence effects. Subgroup analyses of baseline characteristics (biological sex, perceived stress, chronic stress, regular sports activity) will be performed using the "anova" function. Exploratory latent class analyses may reveal new groupings influencing outcome variables.

To explore associations between subjective stress and vagus activity, changes in RMSSD and stress scores will be correlated using Spearman's rho, a non-parametric test used to evaluate ordinal data such as Likert scale responses. The Relaxation State Questionnaire change scores and the change in therapists' RMSSD will also be evaluated using linear mixed-effects models. Interviews will be analyzed by means of qualitative content analysis (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2024; Mayring, 2022).

An interim analysis will be conducted with the first 30 data sets. The study will conclude if the unstandardized effect size is at least a mean difference of 9 ms between treatments ($p \leq 0.001$). The final analysis will maintain a p-value of <0.05 (Peto-Haybittle rule). If necessary, the Holm-Bonferroni method will control for family-wise error rate due to multiplicity of testing on the primary endpoint (Meier, 2022).

Discussion

Contributing to the canon of research comparing live versus pre-recorded music, we explore and integrate psychometric and psychophysiological methods to investigate effects of monochord sounds on the autonomic nervous system response in healthy adults. In assessing this receptive music therapy approach, various psychological concepts, particularly relaxation, along with psychobiological markers such as HRV and EDA, will be examined. The fusion of psychological and psychobiological assessments will offer a comprehensive understanding of the underlying mechanisms of receptive music therapy utilizing monochord sounds for inducing relaxation in healthy adults. Our findings may be applicable to other interventions that examine the effects of live versus pre-recorded music. Comparable approaches include live-improvised receptive music therapy sequences created in the present moment in resonance with

clients, compared to standardized pre-recorded music. Additionally, the qualitative results may contribute to the development in methods incorporating imagery and music. Vibroacoustic approaches could also benefit from this study design, serving as a model for similar research.

In addition, we will explore whether there is a correlation between audio signals and biosignals and whether there is an association between the biosignals of the therapist and those of the participant. Also, investigating live vs. pre-recorded receptive music therapy intervention is a necessary endeavor to better understand the dynamics at play during these commonly used interventions.

Risk mitigation

In individuals with unstable emotion regulation, trauma-induced hypersensitivity, or severe ego-structural disorders, the monochord sounds could trigger a reaction of being overwhelmed and potentially destabilize them. To minimize such risks and ensure appropriate supervision, a doctor is an integral part of the research team who personally conducts the medical history interviews for each potential participant. Overall, our study design has been classified as a low-risk study by the Swiss Ethics Committee.

Strengths and limitations of the study design

This study has several strengths. As a randomized controlled trial, it can potentially demonstrate a causal relationship between exposure to monochord sounds and the elicitation of a potential relaxation response. The crossover design not only requires fewer participants to achieve adequate statistical power but also facilitates the exploration of individual preferences based on exposure to both interventions and allows for the analysis of within-participant effects on HRV metrics, comparison of subjective preferences and experiences during interventions. A key strength of this study is its randomized design, which enables causal inferences and is considered the gold standard for assessing intervention effects. Another strength is the exploratory investigation of the interpersonal phenomenon of synchronicity at both psychological and physiological levels. The inclusion of qualitative methods expands the exploratory approach, with qualitative content analysis potentially generating categories for further investigation. A limitation of this study is the limited number of intervention sessions, which allows only short-term effects to be assessed. Furthermore, the specific age group was chosen based on the physiological rationale that younger age is linked to higher HRV (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1997; Umetani et al., 1998). While this choice supports physiological criteria, it limits generalizability to other age groups. Additionally, due to individual music preferences, the monochord's relaxing effect may vary among participants and could be further analyzed across sub-groups, considering its importance in receptive music therapy interventions.

Potential impact

The study may contribute significantly to the intentional application of live and/or pre-recorded monochord sounds in preventative care for healthy individuals and inform further investigations focusing on individuals with stress-related disorders. Findings gained from healthy participants could contribute to and advance evidence-based receptive music therapy treatments. We expect a deeper understanding concerning the intersubjective experience in the field of receptive music therapy with monochord sounds and live playing could emerge as a key factor in generating social connectedness. We aim to better understand the impact of receptive music therapy approaches on a physiological and psychological level.

Conclusion

We are comparing the effects of live monochord playing and pre-recorded monochord sounds on the autonomic nervous system response in healthy adults. We anticipate that there will be a difference in the HRV measurements, feelings of connection between the therapist and participant, and physiological synchronization between these two interventions, which could inform further research on music therapy's role in promoting stress regulation.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Funding

The Institute for Music Research at the Zurich University of the Arts has provided the start-up funding including costs for the technical equipment and materials. It is also financing part of the wages of the research team. Further third-parties have supported this study financially: The Deutsche Musiktherapeutische Gesellschaft (German Music Therapy Association, DMtG) and other anonymous third party funders. DR has been granted a scholarship to support her PhD studies at AAU from the Department of Psychology and Communication at Aalborg University and from the Andreas Tobias Kind Stiftung in Germany. The authors declare that all study-related processes e.g. including data collection, analysis, interpretation, and publication, will be conducted independently from all the above-mentioned study funders.

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